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BORDERING PATHS FOR THE TEACHING OF VISUAL ARTS IN A DECOLONIAL PERSPECTIVE

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ABSTRACT

This is an exploratory study based on a brief, and still partial, literature review on non-colonial theories for teaching Visual Arts. In large part, it is the result of questions that arose during my doctoral research on image production in Amazonian cultures, and the implications of erasing this visual narrative in art history, and which now unfold in the teaching practices of Visual Arts for students. early years of elementary school. The main objective is to organize a theoretical framework of initial reference, based on concepts that guide a decolonial teaching practice for Art, given the permanence of themes, contents and activities centered on European or North American culture. More specifically, I hope to forge paths capable of shifting the emphasis given to Western art and its canons - taken as the only relevant source of references in the teaching of the Arts -, to other cultures placed in a peripheral situation, and that despite their historical erasure and marginalization, are fundamental sources of knowledge and aesthetic experimentation for the formation of individuals capable of relating artistic production with analysis, historical information and contextualization, so necessary for expanding their visual repertoire and favoring their understanding of the cultural diversity that insists and persists in consolidating itself. as a political practice in the contemporary world.

INTRODUCTION

The teaching of Visual Arts has been marked for some years by conceptual and methodological changes and has been a challenge that instigates and demands changes in perception in relation to its themes and practices, especially in current times, when there is a social, political urgency, ethics and morals regarding processes that decolonize the fields of knowledge in favor of the visibility of different types of knowledge that make up the social fabric. These transformations in teaching also reflect how the scientific discipline of Art History has undergone significant changes, whether from the point of view of its objects of study, or the theories and methods that guide its analyses. As the significant efforts of researchers to incorporate more complex and diverse narratives about global artistic exchanges grow, the inclusion of new objects to the canons of the area also increases and a consequent revision of theoretical-methodological assumptions for the treatment of unique artistic traditions located outside the hegemonic European or North American perspective. In the case of Brazil, these transformations of the discipline seek to correct the lapses left by the exclusion of a significant part of the visual culture of its own territory, since the construction of the field of art history here was carried out via European tradition.

Like the academy, the school is, historically, a space for maintaining the hegemony of knowledge committed to coloniality and both need to be decolonized, bringing to the center of discussions other cultures, their narratives and epistemologies, arts and aesthetics made invisible by force. of the colonial project in disqualifying the diverse as illegitimate, folkloric or naive.

It is true that the National Curricular Parameters established an equivalent weight for Art in terms of importance as a discipline, but this did not even remotely solve the problems of its teaching, since they do not recommend plurality, but are an instrument of homogenization of themes. Another aspect is the teachers' training itself, which still lacks incentives and deepening to minimally guarantee the organization of a teaching practice that is capable of favoring knowledge about Visual Arts that relates artistic production with analysis, historical information and contextualization

(BARBOSA, 2012; MOURA, 2019).

To broaden my understanding of coloniality in art teaching, I turn to authors who explain the insurgency of the term de(s)colonial in the Latin American context, as a sharpening of criticism of the previous terms used to discuss the signs of failure of modernity projects, that is, post - colonial or post - modern problems . I also rely on research carried out in the field of Art Education to situate myself in terms of practices for identifying the dynamics of coloniality in the formation and instrumentalization of this knowledge, so that I can then direct the processes of decolonial practice and thus, possibly transform the parameters of perception and predominantly European or North American readings of the world that are still in force in the construction of imagery repertoires of art.

Following the example of the development possibilities of a decolonial project for teaching the arts in the early years of Fundamental, I bring to this study a design of the actions that I have developed in the learning spaces available at the Vira Virou school and that, despite being an experimental project, still under construction, has favored practical exchanges that I consider important for transforming the repertoires of students, fellow teachers and class assistants, strengthening the notion that guides the principles of the school that, in his words, strives

to build a genuinely Brazilian pedagogical proposal. Thus, in addition to the world knowledge and references that traditionally make up the school curriculum, we seek to add to the content grid the knowledge of Amerindian and African origin of the peoples that constitute our Brazilian identity. Thus, we expanded the references in our curriculum, seeking a richer cultural literacy for our children (Available at <https://www.viravirou.com.br/nossos-diferenciais>).

In this sense, I recognize the privilege of developing this project in an environment that pronounces and welcomes diversity, generating an active and transforming learning community.

THE DECOLONIZATION OF ART HISTORY AS A CONVERSATION STARTER

From research in the field of Visual Arts, I observed the problems of the hegemony of Western thought over other worldviews, their artistic productions and cultural expressions. Interested in studying Amazonian artistic production during my PhD, I did not find theoretical support in the History of Art to build my object. Despite the fact that Amazonian art, in the last forty years, has surpassed the borders of its production sites, meeting the demand of a foreign market voraciously interested in traditional cultures, their knowledge, medicines and in their art, it does not appear in the specialized literature, the not when framed in the category of naïve, naïve art or something like that. To continue the research, I resorted to the Anthropology of Art, a field that is already advanced in discussions about other worlds, cultures and possible cosmovisions. Thus, when I started teaching Visual Arts for elementary school, I already had the conviction that one cannot know about one's own cultural identity, massively studying references alien to one's own culture. And in this regard, there is nothing new, since researchers such as Ana Mae Barbosa have been dealing with the problem since the 1980s, but the need to discuss pedagogical practices that actually transform the colonized scenario of Visual Arts teaching remains pressing and will certainly take more a few years to gain clearer and more permanent decolonial contours.

Being part of a school community that resonates with Brazilian arts and cultures is an opportunity for teaching practice guided by the approach to the relationship between artistic production, historical contexts and unique, distinct and diverse cultural territories in relation to the teaching model guided by colonial. That is, a teaching practice capable of building a knowledge of artistic making that is crossed by the multiplicity of cultures and their

different historical contexts, whose aesthetic references can be rich for learning experiences in the field of Visual Arts, especially in the context of Brazilian culture, but on the other hand, not restricted exclusively to him.

I begin by trying to understand the notion of cultural diversity. The term points to the relatively recent search for the imagination of ways of counter-hegemonic rearticulation of this diversity as the foundation of the struggles of different peoples and of alternative and emancipating regional integration projects, from other, local and community knowledge and experiences and not exclusively cut out in the Eurocentric conception. of being and being in the world. But, according to BARBOSA (2019),

“To define cultural diversity, we have to navigate again through a complex web of terms. Some talk about multiculturalism, others about pluriculturalism, and we still have the most appropriate term - interculturality. While the terms “multicultural” and “pluricultural” mean the coexistence and mutual understanding of different cultures in the same society, the term “intercultural” means the interaction between different cultures. This should be the goal of education interested in cultural development. To achieve this goal, education must provide knowledge about the local culture, the culture of various groups that characterize the nation and the culture of other nations (BARBOSA, 2019. p. 15)”.

Therefore, promoting interculturality is the foundation of an education that values diverse and divergent knowledge, without which it is not possible to understand one's own cultural identity.

Virus Graffiti. Diversity. Acrylic on gable, 2018.

ART AND EDUCATION: DECOLONIAL AESTHETICS FOR FEELING, THINKING AND DOING

Decolonial processes have been crossing the various areas of knowledge and it is no different for Education and Art. In these fields, such processes involve the identification of the dynamics of coloniality that formed and instrumentalized this knowledge, finally allowing one to speak of decoloniality, in the sense of removing from the cognitive and emotional formation of other peoples the inculcation of parameters of perception and readings of the world that reinforce coloniality.

First, it was necessary to recognize coloniality in order to formulate its conceptual and practical antidote. This concept was not born in Europe, which previously launched other terms to explain contemporary processes, such as post-modernity or post-coloniality, as early as the 1950s. SALES and CABRERA (2021) point out that the term post-colonial points to two aspects :

the first concerns the decolonization process of the “Third World” countries in the second half of the 20th century and therefore means liberation, emancipation and independence from imperialism and colonialism. The other strand concerns the postcolonial as a broad epistemic, intellectual and political current (SALES; CABRERA, 2021. p. 4).

With the “colonial tour”, from the 1990s, organized by Latin American intellectuals established in the United States, happening in parallel in Latin America, the proposal was then to radicalize the confrontation and criticism in relation to postcolonial studies and post-structuralists, whose arguments continued to be grounded in Eurocentric thinking and which were being aired in Europe.

MIGNOLO (2017) gives a sense of insurgency, or uprising, to the decolonial proposal by affirming not only the crisis of modernity as a universal project of civilization, but pointing out that this project collapsed from the reactive force that emerged in various parts of the world and projecting itself in the production of artists who greatly perceive the power of the image in the construction and

deconstruction of hegemonic thoughts.

The westernization of the world is no longer possible, because more and more people are resisting being integrated into it. On the contrary, people begin to re-exist. This means imagining a way of living their/our lives instead of donating our bodies and our time to corporations, our attention and our intelligence to the insufferable mainstream media, and our energy to banks [...]. Responses of different types and levels have become visible, including the emergence of de-westernization projects [...] (MIGNOLO, 2017, p. 6).

LEÓN (2019), points out that colonial criticism allows understanding the structural relationship between significant practices - which can be discursive, visual or bodily - and resulting global power structures. As it states,

the decolonial critique has its origins in the debate on the matrices of power generated by colonization in the fields of knowledge, culture, representations and in their constant restructuring, along the different waves of modernization and westernization that Latin America has gone through (LEÓN, 2019, p. 61).

For this study, I will use the term decolonial , and with regard to the variation of the prefixes des or de colonial, as explained by QUINTERO, FIGUEIRA E PAZ CONCHA (2019),

There is no consensus regarding the use of the decolonial/decolonial concept, both forms refer to the dissolution of the structures of domination and exploitation configured by coloniality and the dismantling of its main devices. Aníbal Quijano, among others, prefers to refer to decoloniality, while most authors use the idea of decoloniality . According to Catherine Walsh (WALSH, Catherine (org.). Interculturalidad, Estado, sociedad : luchas (de) coloniales of our time . Quito, University Andean Simón Bolívar/ Abya -Yala, 2009), the suppression of the “s” does not mean the adoption of

an anglicism, but the introduction of a difference in the Castilian “des”, as it is not intended only to disarm or undo the colonial (QUINTERO, FIGUEIRA E PAZ CONCHA, 2019. p.16).

From what has been said, it is clear the need to think of ways to remove the exclusivity of the Western perspective, ethnocentered especially in the European continent, and more recently in the North American continent, shifting the gaze to the borders where the diverse sources of references for the formation of the visual repertoire of students in the early years of elementary school, and offering elements for the knowledge and recognition of their own cultural identity from the teaching of Visual Arts. In this regard, HOMI (1989) apud BARBOSA (2019), clarifies that

“1. Identity is being for oneself and for the other; consequently, identity is found among our differences.” 2. The function of the arts in forming the image of identity gives it a characteristic role among the complex aspects of culture. Identification is always the production of “an image of identity and transformation of the subject by assuming or rejecting that image recognized by the other HOMI, 1989. p.139 apud BARBOSA, 2019. pp. 15 and 16”.

It is enough to pay attention to reality to realize that ways of understanding the world are in dispute. One of them focuses on the vision of a single world, another understands it as being multiple, where other worlds are possible beyond the capitalist organization of social life. This directly implies the perception that there are other cultural, artistic and technical manifestations that are legitimate, original and consistent as an expression of unique, different and divergent worldviews, that is, outside the zone of cultural convergence that organizes the world with a single vision.

For GOMEZ (2019), the place where decoloniality can be operationalized is precisely in the field of education, where the arts, humanities and practices, often excluded or placed in reduced spaces, can find a place of creation that is not subordinated to models colonial.

MOURA’s synthesis (2019) explains that

Thinking about a decolonial Art/ Education does not imply delegitimizing knowledge in art from a European perspective (different from a Eurocentric perspective); necessarily implies legitimizing knowledge in Latin American art. It is not a careless and disconnected look that thinks the art and knowledge of this region inserted in Education, but the understanding from the place of enunciation, Latin America, and, through political consciousness, the potentialization of anti-hegemonic and anti- hierarchical in favor of decolonial thinking/doing/being/feeling (MOURA, 2019. p. 33).

It is not, therefore, a question of excluding European or North American art from the students’ visual culture, but of leading to the construction of a broad knowledge about the multiple aesthetics that are constructed in the world and how they are historically structured. The path is to deconstruct colonial references imprinted in the formation of the cultural identity of other peoples with practices that lead to unlearning these inculcations, and this configures the decolonization of minds from a pedagogy understood as a reflective practice of the meaning of being human, as ALBAN puts it (2009). That is, a pedagogy that allows the expression without restrictions, interdictions or belittlement of different cultures, so that we can disarm what restricts our soul. Alongside this, it is worth remembering what Chimananda Adichie (2018) teaches about the importance of the multiplicity of stories that constitute the many references about being in the world and even about what the world is .

Stories matter. Many stories matter. Stories have been used to plunder and slander, but they can also be used to empower and humanize. They can shatter the dignity of a people, but they can also repair that shattered dignity. [...] [...] I would like to end with this idea: when we reject the single story, when we realize that there is never a single story about anywhere, we regain a kind of paradise (ADCHIE, C. p.16, 2018).

In the field of theories, this brief literature

review, introductory and still reduced, allows me to reflectively think about my practices in teaching the Visual Arts. I believe that as a starting point, it is essential to organize a plan capable of being a map to find ways to promote experiences and practical exchanges that mobilize students' interest, enthusiasm and curiosity, while at the same time feeding my teaching practice with new perceptions about the possibilities that give rhythm to learning situations in Art and Culture.

ART, EDUCATION AND CULTURE IN THE GAPS: PLANNING THE TEACHING OF VISUAL ARTS IN A BRAZILIAN CHILDHOOD SCHOOL

Ana Mae Barbosa, since the 1980s, questioned the universality of hegemonic codes in favor of plurality as an articulating principle of knowledge and drew attention to “respect for diversity: diversity of cultural codes; biological diversity, generating expectations of ecological balance; diversity of interpretations and readings of art (BARBOSA, 1998. p.11)”. For her, the key to this transformation lies in education as a place for the development of different cultural codes. In addition, it points out that art in education, as a personal expression and as culture, is an important instrument for cultural identification and the development of perception and imagination, apprehension of the reality of the environment, the development of critical capacity, favoring the analysis perceived reality in order to transform it creatively.

And from this point of view, I consider fundamental a teaching practice that prioritizes art as an element of cultural expression, capable of teaching about the plurality of cultures, considering

that characterize the society or social group, its way of life, its value system, its traditions and beliefs. Art, as a presentational language of the senses, transmits meanings that cannot be

transmitted through any other type of language, such as discursive and scientific languages (BARBOSA, op. cit. p. 16)”.

And beyond that, it is necessary to consider art as an element in the relationship between different cultures and everyday life, not just from the point of view of the aesthetic experience or places of legitimation, such as museums, since these are not universal concepts for all cultures, but as an ethical principle that guides their existence in the world, as the Amerindian peoples do, for example. Thus, the annual planning of the Arts discipline was based on the relationship between the themes of Brazilian art - in their diversity in the times and spaces of the formation of Brazilian culture -, and their visual repertoires (the artistic works themselves) with the contexts (time and space) of their creation, seeking to bring students closer to the biography of the artists, the culture they speak of, their ways of living and producing art, their various techniques, materials and aesthetic expressions. It is important to point out that the planning was oriented in line with the main topics addressed by the regent teachers, especially with regard to topics related to African and Amerindian cultures, making Art activities instruments for the study of other cultural and aesthetic expressions.

ANNUAL PLANNING OF THE DISCIPLINE FOR 2022

Below, I reproduce the menus created for a summary of the discipline's annual planning. As an annex, I provide the weekly table of activities developed. Some photographic records follow on the cover of this work.

Visual Arts quarterly plan 2022 Mar/Apr/May

Composition. Alexandre Mancini, 2016. Above: Multiethnic Mural, detail. Kobra, 2016. Below: Mermaid. Alfredo Volpi, 1960.

Menu: Artistic, aesthetic languages and their knowledge. Art as language. Elements and languages of the visual arts. History of Art to get out of coloniality. Knowledge and development of techniques and materials through artistic practices.

General objective: to present the elements of the languages of the visual arts, continuously involving the interaction between different systems necessary for communication and expression.

Specific objectives: Promoting a non-colonial look at artistic production, making known an overview of the visual arts by exploring the artistic production of Brazilian and foreign painters, sculptors, weavers, engravers, embroiderers, digital artists, designers and illustrators.

Methodology: expository classes from the history of art, placing at the center of the learning process the arts of Latin America, Brazil, its popular culture, but including the relevant productions of Western European art, which are much more available, but not unique for the formation of a thought about art, processes and practices in visual arts and student research.

Jun/Jul/Aug

General objective: to offer from the culture and art of the Jequitinhonha Valley, a place (territory) of

research and knowledge in Popular Art, and to promote from this, the accuracy of the capacity for invention and artistic creation for students. Reaffirm the elements of the visual arts: dots, lines, colors, shapes. Stimulate aesthetic perception in order to expand the visual repertoires about culture. Observe the diversity of Brazilian artistic production.

Menus:

2nd quarter (June to August)

Brazilian Popular Art. Folk Art and Culture. Art or craft? Contemporary Popular Art in Brazil. Artists, languages, materials and techniques of popular art. Above right: Washerwomen. Matizes Dumont. Embroidery.

No author. Next: Flags. Alfredo Volpi. Below: Festa Junina. Detail. Mary Help of Christians. Washerwomen. Heitor de Pleasures.

Objectives: offer subsidies for the construction of knowledge and meanings about popular art and its various forms of expression. Show masters of Brazilian culture and popular art. Favoring the development of aesthetic perception and motor skills through artistic creation activities, expanding the repertoire of references on art production in Brazil.

3rd trimester (September to November)

Upper range: Pieces from the Cooperativa de Artesãos de Campo Alegre and sieve for clay. Intermediate range: Invented Animals from Lira Marques (Araçuaí) and guarantor of the Berilo Community. Bottom band: cotton and Beryl loom. Below: Museum of Frei Chico and Lira Marques in Araçuaí and novels produced in Berilo. Jequitinhonha Valley, 2022.

What is Art? Art as historical and cultural heritage of humanity. Art as a product of history and the multiplicity of human cultures. Art as a language and symbolic system of representation (shapes, lines, colors, planes, symbols, points). Art as resistance. Significant Art Appreciation. Art in its diversity: Latin American arts, African arts, Australian aboriginal arts and Brazilian art. Contemporary aspects since they are alive and reinvent themselves. Colonization and art. Who tells the art story? Brazilian art in relation to European art. Modern art in Brazil. What was the Week of 22?

Above: Congadeiros. Marcio Cintra. Below: African Geometry. No author.

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Objectives: to recognize contents, styles and concepts of Art, gaining tools for artistic making itself. Stimulate students' reflection and favor the understanding of the artistic phenomenon as an object of culture through history and as a set of formal relationships.

ALONG THE WAY

More specifically, and following the teaching interests of the school community globally, the central axis of the Arts discipline was guided by the study of Brazilian popular art produced in the Jequitinhonha Valley, in Minas Gerais, although not exclusively. From the field experience carried out with the artists of the Valley in July 2022, I proposed for the end of the 2nd quarter and beginning of the 3rd quarter, the deepening of experiences of the relationship between history, context and artistic production, developing an affective research with the students, in the sense of affecting them with the discoveries of the trip. For this, I organized the exhibition of pieces of popular art relating them to the history (and image) of the artists who produced them, their contexts, exploring the variety of their techniques and materials. The sequence below describes the themes and their approaches. Some have already been worked on in the different grades according to the age group and their skills and competences, others are still in progress and some points may not be addressed exactly as planned, since the planning is live and can/should be changed from the demands of students and teachers in view of an integrated project of study and learning.

Organizing axes :

1. Living Museum. Sharing information about the art and culture of the Valley, observation and handling of the art pieces brought. Ceramics, tapestry, embroidery, basketry, wood carving and iron sculpture. Artists of the Valley: biography, materials, techniques and artistic production.

2. Ceramics and painting with earth paints in Lira Marques. Imaginary animals inspired by the Animals of My Sertão, by Lira Marques. Studio experiences: Drawing and painting with pastel chalk on special paper. Production of a handmade booklet with images of imaginary animals for the 1st year classes.

3. Earth paints. Studio experiences: painting clay pieces brought from the Valley with earth paint produced by 4th and 5th grade students.

4. The tradition of dolls in D. Izabel, Glória and Andréia (three generations of dollmakers). Modeling exercise of a "doll in the pot", inspired by the popular contemporary work of the artist Andréia, granddaughter of D. Izabel.

5. From cotton to thread, from thread to fabric: spinners and weavers. Handling cotton in the classroom, the natural colors of cotton, plants used to dye yarn. Testimonials by Dona Selma and the weavers of Berilo. Spinning and weaving videos. Photos of the looms and the pieces produced.

6. Embroiderers and threads that tell stories. Atelier experience: drawings from embroidery. Embroider a simple design with elementary stitches: basting. Note: Embroidery needles have well-rounded tips.

SOME FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Utopias aside, these reflections are part of my daily life and I believe that it is even possible to transform mentalities from teaching Art and Culture as decolonial practices. I don't consider it an easy or simple task, but there's nothing left to wait for to promote changes in education, to misalign what is given, bringing to the forefront new symmetries that guarantee the visibility of other essential knowledge for good living.

Supported by theories, concepts, terms and practices that are organized as a counter-discourse, I bet on the political option of decoloniality as an opportune path for education in Latin America, as it was the result of the concerns of Latin American thinkers that emerged in the critique of the binomial modernity/ coloniality, to which all other peoples were subjected and from which they now have the chance to free themselves. And in this sense, I understand the importance of Art and Culture as places of collective social engagement, as instruments of knowledge and recognition of diverse cultural, artistic, aesthetic, ethical and political identities.

From the point of view of my teaching experiences at the Vira Virou school, I have had

a stimulating opportunity to be able to develop the concept, activities and teaching practices with academic freedom, within an environment where there is respect and dialogue, fundamental elements to horizontalize peer relations and ensure that the essentials for thought-provoking, critical and transformative learning situations.

As has been said, the transformations in the teaching of the Arts have brought new challenges to the practices of the school community. This also leads me to think about the specific learning spaces of Art, be it an Art Room or an Atelier, and what is the need for this space for the development of studies, techniques and artistic processes. Is its constitution important from the point of view of more lasting and consistent practical exchanges? To what extent? There are several studies dedicated to this issue, although a more vertical discussion on the subject is not within the scope of this article. But it is worth noting that, similarly to the laboratories constituted for robotics studies, for example, which are legitimate and stimulate scientific and critical thinking so fundamental for a transformative education, it seems quite natural to me that there are spaces constituted for a discipline that deals with processes not always fast, whose techniques and materials are so diverse, as well as the possible didactic resources are multiple. Until when, despite advances in education, will it be necessary to develop this continuous process of building knowledge in adapted environments? What is the priority given to spaces for the continuous development of the Arts in schools? How to create conditions for the formation of a permanent learning space for the arts?

These basic questions, which are discussed in theory but not always materialized in practice, point to the permanence of this utopian topic: ensuring the full existence of a space that meets the needs of research activities and the development of more continuous practices, less interrupted by questions of the limited class time, which allows the prior organization of the tables with materials, which contain a space for drying the produced pieces, which includes some space for the exhibition of the works. I imagine this space as being stimulating, capable of welcoming children's expansiveness and that it is conducive to mediation with students that is less tense and richer from the point of view of learning, experiences and practical exchanges;

where circulation is allowed, where guidance on the activities to be carried out can be efficiently communicated to the student, avoiding wasting time in exhausting repetitions done in high volume and generating more profitable results, serving the theoretical and practical learning of the arts. This is also decolonizing, supporting and legitimizing the field of Art Education within school communities as a territory for training and transforming critical social agents, but at the same time, sensitive ones.

Finally, the theme of this article does not end here and with the objective of expanding this discussion through dialogue with other researchers, this work was enrolled in the V International Seminar on Research in Arts and Visual Culture, in the thematic axis Education, Art and Culture view, which will be promoted by the Federal University of Goiás and Universidad de la Republica Uruguay, and will take place remotely, on December 8th and 9th, 2022.

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